

Parents' involvement in Children's Education: A Study on Kachua Upazila of Bagerhat, Bangladesh

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to assess the parents' involvement in their children's education. Survey method was used to get information from the parents of different unions of Kachua Upazila, Bagerhat, Bangladesh. A total of 200 parents were selected from seven unions of Kachua Upazila. The study followed multistage sampling technique for selecting the study area. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data which were analyzed using SPSS 20.0 software. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used in it. The study has found that involvement of the parents mostly depends on the educational quality and financial ability of the parents. It also found that women are more engaged in children's educational affairs than that of men and most of the women (89.58%) spend time regularly for their children's study. It also reveals that 7% parents cannot ensure good environment of studying of their children at home, 20.5% parents cannot ensure home tutor, 5% cannot fulfill essential needs of the children and 31% parents spend less than 500 taka per month for their children's academic purpose. The main cause of this scenario is 44.5% parents' monthly income is below 10,000 taka. This study also found that 96% parents provide equal facilities to both sons and daughter and 96.5% parents think about higher education of their children. It reveals that rural parents are less involved than urban parents in children's study. Overall the study revealed that, most of the parents of Kachua Upazila are not involve enough in their children's academic activities. The study recommends that parents of rural area should be more involved in their children's educational activities as they are the children's first educator.

Key Words: *Parents, Involvement, Consciousness, Children, Education, Study.*

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Introduction

Parents are the first and continuing educators of their children. They are also the closest person of children. Children's growth, socialization, behavior mostly depend on their parents. Like this, proper education of children also depends on their parent's consciousness and involvement in children education. Conscious parents can help their children's academic study. Parental encouragement and support for learning activities at home combined with parental involvement in schooling is critical to children's education. Parents' involvements in children academic education improve the educational quality of a child William (2007).

On the other hand, a lot of students are dropped out from school because of the unconsciousness of their parents. Sometimes children have enough potentiality of learning in education but they fail to do that because they do not get enough support from their parents. This problem is severe in rural area. In urban area parents are conscious enough on their children education. They actively get involve in children all academic activities. For this reason, children from urban area can get more opportunity of proper education. (Barnard, 2003)

Most of the people of Bangladesh live in rural area. According to the World Bank collection of development indicators, this number is 64.96% in 2016. But educational quality of rural area is not standard enough. There are many reasons behind this problem. One of these is lacking of parents involvement in children education.

It is very difficult to improve the educational quality of a country without making the parents conscious on their children. By involving children's study they can be more conscious. If parents engage in children's academic study, quality of primary education can be improved. Otherwise children will fail to be strong enough in their primary education. If children become weak in their primary education, it will be difficult for them to continue their studies. For this reason, a lot of children dropped out from school in Bangladesh. Many parents think that, if their children earn money or support family, it will be better for their children to be involved in earning money than in education. But urban area shows an opposite situation where parents take care of their children properly, take interest in their studies to help, support and inspire them. As a result these urban children can achieve their academic goals easily.

Literature Review

Parents' involvement in child education is shown all over the world. But involvement level and process varies according to society and country as well. Some research work has been done in this field by different scholars.

Jeynes (2012), shows in his research that there is a close relationship between various kinds of parental involvement programs and the academic achievement of pre-kindergarten-12th-grade school children. Analyses determined the effect sizes for various parental involvement programs overall and subcategories of involvement. Results indicate a significant relationship between parental involvement programs overall and

academic achievement, both for younger and older students as well as for four types of parental involvement programs.

William (2007), points out in his study the influence of parental involvement on the educational outcomes of urban secondary school children. Statistical analyses are done to determine the overall impact of parental involvement as well as its specific components. Four different measures of educational outcomes are used. These measures include an overall measure of all components of academic achievement combined, grades, standardized tests, and other measures that generally included teacher rating scales and indices of academic attitudes and behaviours. The possible differing effects of parental involvement by race and socioeconomic status are also examined. The results indicate that the influence of parental involvement overall is significant for secondary school children. Parental involvement as a whole affects all the academic variables under study by about .5 to .55 of a standard deviation unit. The positive effects of parental involvement hold for both White and minority children.

Gaviria (2015), point out a quantitative synthesis of research into parental involvement and academic achievement through a meta-analysis of 37 studies in kindergarten, primary and secondary schools carried out between 2000 and 2013. Effect size estimations were obtained by transforming Fisher's correlation coefficient. An analysis has also been conducted of the heterogeneity of the magnitudes grouped according to different moderator variables, and a study of the publication bias affecting meta-analytical studies. The results show that the parental models most linked to high achievement are those focusing on general supervision of the children's learning activities. The strongest associations are found when the families have high academic expectations for their children, develop and maintain communication with them about school activities, and help them to develop reading habits.

Barnard (2003), explained in his study that parents involvement in school (based on teacher and parent reports) and parents reports of home involvement were used to determine if greater reported parent involvement was associated with indicators of school success. Results indicated that even after controlling for background characteristics and risk factors, parent involvement in school was significantly associated with lower rates of high school dropout, increased on-time high school completion, and highest grade completed. This study suggests that parent involvement in school is an important component in early childhood education to help and promote long-term effects.

Smith, Joanna, Kuzin (2011), point out the benefits of parent involvement in education. However, research has also shown that White, middle-class parents are disproportionately involved. Charter schools, as schools of choice, have been assumed to have fewer involvement barriers for minority and low-income parents, but a 2007 survey of charter leaders found that parent involvement remains a significant challenge. This qualitative study utilizes Epstein's model of family involvement to examine parent

involvement programs at twelve charter schools across six U.S. states. Findings suggest that parent involvement "activities" in the study sample of urban charter schools fit Epstein's typology fairly well. However, the "strategies" used to implement these activities and to attract hard-to-reach parents are fairly innovative: Study schools offered wrap-around services, incentives, and contracts to enhance and ensure participation; utilized technology for advertising parent volunteer opportunities; and involved parents in the decision-making and governance of the school. Overall, these strategies were linked with increasing parents' self-efficacy and comfort level in participating in their children's education.

Dempsey, Sandler (1997), mention in this research why parents become involved in their children's elementary and secondary education. Three major constructs are believed to be central to parents' basic involvement decisions. First, parents' role construction defines parents' beliefs about what they are supposed to do in their children's education and appears to establish the basic range of activities that parents construe as important, necessary, and permissible for their own actions with and on behalf of children. Second, parents' sense of efficacy for helping their children succeed in school focuses on the extent to which parents believe that through their involvement they can exert positive influence on their children's educational outcomes. Third, general invitations, demands, and opportunities for involvement refer to parents' perceptions that the child and school want them to be involved. Hypotheses concerning the functioning of the three constructs in an additive model are suggested, as are implications for research and practice. Overall, the review suggests that even well-designed school programs inviting involvement will meet with only limited success if they do not address issues of parental role construction and parental sense of efficacy for helping children succeed in school.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of this research are-

1. To find out the parents involvement in their children's education in rural area.
2. To identify which types of people of Kachua area more conscious on their children.
3. To determine how much time do the parent spend on their children's education?
4. To examine, the financial ability of rural parents to bear the educational expenses.

Theoretical Framework

In social learning theory, Albert Bandura (1977) agrees with the behaviourist learning theories of classical conditioning and operant conditioning. There are some relationships between Bandura - Social Learning Theory and Parents Involvement on their children education. Some of those are given below.

Children learn through observation

Bandura's Social Learning Theory says that people especially in infant age learn through observation. Most of the children pass their childhood with parents. Children observe all activities of the parents. Parents' activities impact on the mind of a child. And most of the children take their parents as a model subconsciously. If the parents become conscious about their behaviour before their sons or daughter, children will be able to learn good manner.

Children make someone model

Generally Children's subconscious minds make their parents a model and they learn from their model. Children behaviour is mostly influenced by their parents. This study is about parents' consciousness about their children education. If they aware about their activities or behaviour with their children, children will learn something from their parents.

Children practice those which they observe: As most of the children observe the activities of their parents, they practice those behaviour or activities which they have learn from their parents. So parents should be aware about their activities before children. They can read book, talk about different educative issues, telling educative stories so that children can observe those and practice in their lives.

In above sense there is a close relationship between Bandura's Social Learning Theory and Parents involvement in their children education.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted through survey research design to collect primary data that were collected during August-September 2019. Data was analysed and interpreted by using descriptive as well as inferential statistical techniques. Different computer software's like SPSS, MS Excel, MS Word etc. were used for analysing and interpretation of data.

This study is conducted in Kachua Municipality of Bagerhat District of Bangladesh to assess involvement level of parents about their children's education. This area has been selected for easy access and being the first Municipality of Bagerhat District.

The study followed multistage sampling technique for selecting the study area. Firstly, Bagerhat district was purposively selected from the southwest region of Bangladesh. Then Kachua municipality area has been chosen purposively.

There are seven unions in this municipality. This study consider seven groups of people as population who are the residents of seven unions: KachuaSadar, Badhal, Raripara, Gopalpur, Moghia, Dhopakhal and Gazalia. Data were collected randomly from every union.

Table 1:*Distribution of Samples*

SL No	Union Name	No of Sample
1	Badhal	30
2	Dhopakhali	30
3	Gazalia	30
4	Gopalpur	30
5	KachuaSadar	20
6	Moghia	30
7	Raripara	30
	Total Sample	200

A structured interview schedule was prepared to collect basic information and to assess consciousness level of respondent. In order to assess the consciousness level of the parents, respondents were asked different questions on different dimensions. All answer were taken in a form. For assessing parents involvement. For secondary data, important information was collected from different scholarly articles.

Table 2:*Socio-economic and demographic variables*

Name of Variable	Measurement Unit	Method of Data Collection
Parents Personal Information	Child Personal Information	
Name:	Name:	
Village:	Age:	
Union:	Sex:	
Occupation:	Institution:	
Education:	Class:	
Age:	Roll:	Structured interview
Monthly Income:	Parents' Cell No:	
Age:		Schedule

Involvement level assessing parameters

Level of parents time spending	Asking question about time spending of parents regarding children's academic purpose.	
Level of ensuring good environment of the study	Asking question about educational environment of the children at home.	
Parents role during different situation	Asking question about the roles of parents in different situation e.g. good time, bad time	
Parents engaged in school	Asking question about the parents involvement like taking part teacher-guardian meeting, talking to teacher etc.	Structured interview
Parents financial contribution	Asking question about money expend of the parents regarding children academic purpose.	Schedule
Power of controlling in different situation.	Asking question about the role of parents in some power controlling situation like watching televising, using mobile phone, administering daily activities.	

Results

Table 3:
Guardian's time spending and ensuring environment

Variables	Participants Percentage	&
Regular time spending by the parents		
Yes	123 (61.5%)	
No	77 (38.5%)	
Amount of time spending of respondents		
Above 2 hours	46 (23%)	
One hour to two	58 (29%)	
Thirty One Minutes To One Hour	56 (28%)	
Less than thirty minutes	40 (20%)	
Ensuring good environment for studying of the children		
Can	115 (57.5%)	
Cannot	14 (7.0%)	
Averagely	71 (35.5%)	
Can	115 (57.5%)	
Roll of parents when their children obtain bad and good results in the examination		
Punishment	57 (28.5%)	
Console And Inspire	127 (63.5%)	
Nothing	16 (8.0%)	

Data presented in the table 1 shows the number of the respondents who spend time regularly for the academic purpose of their children. Majority guardians (61.5%) spend time regularly for the academic purpose of their children where 38.5% do not spend time regularly. Among 200 respondents 152 (76%) are male and 48 (24%) are female. Among 48 female 43 female guardians (89.58%) spend time regularly whereas 80 male guardians (64%) out of 152 spend time regularly for their children's. Here 20% respondents spend less than thirty minutes per day and thirty one minutes to one hour time is spent by 28% guardians on the other hand 29% respondents spend one hour to two hour time and this is the highest ratio of respondent who spend time more than others and 23% respondents spends more than 2 hours. There is a close relationship between the time spending and children's academic performance Jeynes (2012). The parents who spend more the two hours per day with children for academic purpose, these children are among top five in the class.

The table also displays the efficiency of the parents ensuring good environment for the study of their children at home. It shows that 115 (57.5%) respondents can ensure good environment of study for their children. Again 71 respondents (35.5%) can averagely provide this facility to their children. But 7% guardians cannot provide good environment for the study of their children at all. Different parents plays different roll when their children cut sorry figure in the examination. 57 parents (28.5%) punish their children when they obtain bad results in their examination. On the other hand 63.5% guardians console and inspire their children at that moment. But 8% parents do not do anything when their children earn bad results.

Table 4:

Parents controlling to their children

Variables	Participants & Percentage
Pressurizing the children for academic purpose	
Regularly Pressurize	116 (58%)
Sometimes Pressurize	43 (21.5%)
Not Pressurize at all	41 (20.5%)
Parents controlling of using mobile phone of the child	
Use Mobile Phone	23 (11.5%)
Control using mobile phone	10 (5%)
Don't Control using mobile phone	13 (6.5%)
Talking to teachers about the child's academic condition	
Regularly	96 (48%)
Not at all	22 (11%)
Occasionally	42 (41%)
Joining the teachers-guardians meeting	
Regularly	98 (49%)
Not at all	44 (22%)
Occasionally	58 (29%)

There are negative and positive effects of pressuring the children for study. Among 200 respondent 116 guardians (58%) often pressurize their children. They believe that children do not have enough knowledge of reality. If they do not pressurize their children, they fail to do their duties properly. So there is necessity of pressurizing the children. On the other hand, 21.5% guardians occasionally pressurize their children. They believe, pressurizing the children at all time can bring a bad results and not pressurizing any time also can bring a bad results. So they pressurize the children occasionally like during examination period whereas 20.5 guardians do not pressurize their children. There are two reasons behind it. First reason is some parents are totally unconscious of their children education so they do not pressurize them and second reasons is some parents believe children should be encouraged not pressurized. Using mobile phone of the children is one of the major concerns of the parents. Now a days a

lot of children are addicted to the mobile phone and this severely affects the study of the children. But the positive thing is among 200 students; only 23 students (11.5%) use mobile phone. Among 23 the mobile phone user students, 5% are controlled by their parents and the other 6.5% guardians cannot control the using of mobile phone of their children. By talking to the teacher one can get the proper information of academic information of the child. 96 respondent (48%) often talk to the teachers of the school about the academic condition of their children and 82 respondents (41%) do it occasionally. But 22 guardians (11%) cannot talk to the teacher at all. This study noticed that the students, whose parents talk to the teachers, are academically sound than other students. School authority arranges teachers-guardians meeting on different issues in different time. By taking part in the meeting parents can contribute on decision making of the school. This table also shows that 49.5% guardians regularly take part in this meeting and 29% occasionally. On the other hand 21.5% cannot join the meeting. Among the 21% parents most of them are male and engaged in official job or day labour. Female guardians can take part in more than male guardian.

Table 5:

Distribution of satisfaction of the children with their requirement

Variables	Participants & Percentage
Fulfilment of child's requirement with due time	
Can	98 (49%)
Cannot	44 (22%)
Sometimes Cannot	58 (29%)
Ensuring home tutor for the child	
Ensure Home Tutor	130 (65%)
Occasionally	29 (14.5%)
Cannot Ensure	41 (20.5%)
Controlling the watching television of the children	
Yes	141 (70.5%)
No	19 (9.5%)
Sometimes	40 (20%)
Equal facilities of education to both son and daughter	
Provide equal facilities	192 (96%)
Do not equal facilities	8 (4%)

Every student needs many kinds of essential things e.g. dress, book, pen, paper, bag etc. It is important to ensure these needs with due time. This chart shows that 141 respondents (70.5%) can ensure these to their children with due time and 24.5% respondents sometimes cannot ensure it at proper time. But 5% respondent cannot ensure

it at all because of their poverty. Home tutor is an important guide of a child. Home tutors can improve the overall condition of a child. But a people cannot manage home tutor for many causes. Main reason is poverty. This table shows that 130 respondents (65%) can ensure home tutor for their children regularly and 29 respondents (14.5%) can occasionally. But 41 parents (20.5%) cannot ensure home tutor for their children. Watching television has both positive and negative impact for the children. Controlled watching can be beneficial on the other hand uncontrolled habit can affect the children's study severely. In this table 141 respondents (70.5%) can control the watching television of their children and 20% respondent can do it occasionally whereas 9.5% respondent cannot control the watching television of their children. Gender discrimination is one of the most talkative issues in the present era. Gender equality in all sectors of life is must for development. It's also very much important in family. Figure17 shows that 96% respondents provide equal facilities to both son and daughter. But 8 respondents (4%) do not provide equal facilities to them.

Table 6:*Guardians' expenditure and income*

Variables	Participants & Percentage
Monthly money spent for children's academic purpose (Taka)	
0 to 500	63 (31.5%)
501 to 1500	87 (43.5%)
1501 to 2500	30 (15%)
Above 2500	21 (10.5%)
Monthly income of the respondents(Taka)	
0 to 10,000	89 (44.5%)
11k to 20k	76 (38%)
21k to 30k	30 (15%)
Above 30k	5 (2.5%)
Parents' enforcing the child in work avoiding study	
Yes	28 (14%)
No	110 (55%)
Sometimes	62 (31%)
Problem solving of the children	
Often	61 (30.5%)
As per need	107 (53.5%)
Sometimes	31 (15.5%)
Not at all	1 (.5%)

Money is one of the key factors that help a person to take some good initiatives for his children. This chart portrays that 31.5% respondents spends below five hundred BDT for a child per month, 43.5% respondents spend tk501 to 1500 taka. This ratio is the top among these. 15% respondents spend taka 1501 to 2500 taka and only 10.5% respondents spend above twenty five hundred taka. This is too poor to need. It does not mean guardians have enough money but they do not spend. This is for the financial inability of the respondents. There is a close relationship between this expenditure and income of the respondents.

Among 200 respondent 89 respondents (44.5%) earn below ten thousands taka per month. Monthly income of 38% respondents is eleven thousands to twenty thousand taka. 15% respondents earn twenty one to thirty thousand taka per month and only 2.5% guardians' monthly income is above thirty one thousands taka. Sometimes when the children are engaged in study, they are enforced by their parents to do other work such as helping them in farming, fishing, marketing, doing household work etc. It hampers the study of the students. 14% respondents enforce their children when they are engaged in study. 31% parents do it occasionally but the positive thing is 55% respondents do not enforce their children. Different types of problem can be arisen in different situation and this can affect the study of the children. If the problem is solved in due time, no one will be affected. 30.5% respondents can solve the problem when the problem is arisen. 53.5% respondents solve it as per need and 15.5 do it occasionally. Among 200 respondent only 1 person cannot solve the problem at all.

Table 7:

Parent's inspiration and suggestion to their child

Variables	Participants & Percentage
Parent's inspiration to their children for career	
Children inspire about their career	138 (69%)
Do not inspire their children	27 (13.5%)
Sometimes inspire their children	35 (17.5%)
Thinking about higher education of children	
Both son and daughter think about their higher education	185 (92.5%)
Son thinks about their higher education	8 (4%)
Do not thinks about their higher education	7 (3.5%)
Taking suggestion from anyone about the children's study	
Take suggestion	159 (79.5%)
Don't take suggestion	41 (20.5%)
Suggestion of guardians to their child	

Suggest to their children	76 (38%)
Suggest as per the necessity to their children	69 (34.5%)
Suggest sometimes	50 (25%)
Do not suggest their children	5 (2.5%)

Parents can be involved in children's education by different ways. One of these is inspiration and motivation. Table 5 shows that 69% respondent inspire their children about their career. On the other hand guardians do not inspire their children at all. But Among 200 respondents, 35 guardians sometimes inspire their children. Higher education is dream for every child. To be higher educated, parents' inspiration, effort are very much important. In this chart 185 respondents (92.5%) think about the higher education of both son and daughter. But 4% respondents believe that only son should acquire higher education. On the other hand 7 respondents (3.5%) do not think about the higher education of both son and daughter.

Many parents don't have sufficient knowledge about the education as well as the future of the children. For this reason they have to talk to other for it. This table says that 159 respondents (79.5%) take suggestion from other about their children. On the other hand 20.5% respondents don't take suggestion from other. This table discloses the level of giving suggestion of the respondent to the child. Here 76 respondents (38%) often give suggestion to their children. On the other hand 69 guardians (34.5%) give it as per the necessity of the children. They believe, giving suggestion at all time is irritating to their children. So they give suggestion according to the necessity of their children. Again 50 respondents (25%) do it sometimes and 5 guardians do not suggest their children at all. There is a close relationship between the ratio of giving suggestion and educational quality of the parents.

Discussion

Parents are the closest persons of a child. Every child learns more from their parents than other people in the society in its childhood. Generally parents are visualized in a child's behaviour because children observe the attitude of their parents and practice that in their lives. In this sense child education also depends on its parents. But the involvement level of parents in children's education varies from country to country, society to society, region to region. This study aims to know the involvement level of the parents on their children education of Kachua Upazila of Bagerhat district.

Findings of the present study reveal that Majority guardians (61.5%) spend time regularly for the academic purpose of their children where 38.5% do not spent time regularly. 20% respondents spend less than thirty minutes per day and thirty one minutes to one hour time is spent by 28% guardians on the other hand 29% respondents spend one hour to two hour time and this is the highest ratio of respondent who spend time more than others and 23% respondents spends more than 2 hours.

Money is an important factor in education. 7% parents cannot ensure good environment of studying of their children at home, 20.5% parents cannot ensure home tutor, 5% cannot fulfil essential needs of the children, 11% parents cannot provide tiffin cost to their children and 31% parents spent less than 500 taka per month for their children's academic purpose due to poverty because 44.5% parents' monthly income is below 10,000 taka.

Controlling of children in different situation is also an important parameter of parents' involvement. This study has found that (58%) parents administer the home work of their children regularly whereas 84 respondents (42%) do not do it at all. Again the highest number of the respondent (38.5%) often looks after the daily works of the children where 34% respondent always does it. 92.5% parents control using mobile phone and 70.5% can control the watching television of their children.

Connection with school and teacher of the parents is also important for conscious parents. 48% parents regularly talk to the teachers of the school about the academic condition of their children and 41% do it occasionally. In addition 49.5% guardians regularly take part in this meeting and 29% occasionally.

Overall the study revealed that, most of the parents of Kachua Upazila are not involve enough in their children's academic activities. To improve the educational condition of the society parents should be more involved in their children's education.

Conclusion

We know education is the backbone of a nation. No nation can be developed without proper education. To ensure proper education of a nation, it is important to concentrate on children education. But it is very difficult to ensure standard education of children without proper involvement of parents or engagement in children educational activities. Parents can play heroic role to improve the primary education of a society by involving in it. So parent's involvement in children's education should be increased.

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